

Perceived Supervision Scale (PSS) – Chichewa Version

Chonde Fotokezerani momwe mukugwirizirana nalo funso kapena ayi molingana ndi omwe amakuyang'anirani. **Yankhani funso lili lonse pochonga kabokosi osasiya kabokosi kalikonse osachonga.**

	Ndikutsut sana nazo Kwambiri	Ndikutsus ana nazo	Sindinapange chiganizo	Ndikuvomer ezana nazo	Ndikuvomere zana nazo kwambiri
	1	2	3	4	5
1. Yemwe amandiyang'anira amakumana nane kawirikawiri	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Yemwe amandiyang'anira amandiyamikira	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Yemwe amandiyang'anira amakumana nane kawirikawiri kukambirana za mavuto ndi momwe tingathetsere mavutowo	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Yemwe amandiyang'anira amamva maganizo anga	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Yemze amandiyang'anira amadziwa kulumikizana ndi anthu	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Yemwe amandiyang'anira amandithandiza kuwonjezera nzeru pa ntchito yanga	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>